

EBFMC25-OP-53 · Evaluation of Patients Receiving Nicotine Spray Treatment in a Smoking Cessation Clinic

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Smoking remains a significant global public health issue, causing millions of deaths annually (Nides, 2020). Smoking cessation clinics offer a variety of individualized therapeutic options tailored to patient-specific characteristics. Nicotine spray is one such method known for its effectiveness in smoking cessation (Sandhu, 2023). This study aimed to evaluate the sociodemographic characteristics, smoking cessation outcomes, and side effects experienced by patients using nicotine spray therapy.

Methods: The study was conducted retrospectively at Şişli Etfal Hospital's Smoking Cessation Clinic between February 1st, 2025, and February 28th, 2025. Data from patients who applied to the clinic within the last six months of 2024 and initiated nicotine spray therapy were reviewed. Sociodemographic data (age, gender, presence of chronic diseases, employment status), smoking dependency levels (Fagerström Test for Nicotine Dependence - FTND scores), smoking intensity (pack-years), daily nicotine spray usage, smoking cessation outcomes, and treatment-related side effects were recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, and a p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Data from 67 patients who initiated nicotine spray therapy were analyzed. Twenty-two patients were excluded due to withdrawal from treatment, perceived lack of treatment necessity, or financial inability to obtain the spray. The final analysis included 45 patients, with a mean age of 40.77 ± 13.89 years (range: 18–62) and an average FTND score of 4.73 ± 2.78 (range: 0–10). The mean daily nicotine spray usage was 4.53 ± 1.72 puffs (range: 1–10). Side effects related to nicotine spray usage occurred in 7 patients (15.5%), with nausea (n=2, 4.4%) and throat dryness (n=2, 4.4%) being the most frequent. Fifteen patients (33.3%) successfully quit smoking. No statistically significant associations were identified between smoking cessation success and age, gender, chronic disease presence, employment status, smoking intensity, or FTND scores ($p>0.05$). Additionally, no significant associations were found between daily spray usage amount or the occurrence of side effects and completion of treatment ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: In this study, nicotine spray therapy was well-tolerated by most patients, with mild and infrequent side effects. Although nicotine spray is considered a reliable and feasible therapeutic option, larger prospective studies are needed to evaluate its impact on smoking cessation success more definitively.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Nicotine spray, smoking cessation, side effect

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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